

www.arseam.com

Impact Factor: 2.625

DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.293794>

Cite this paper as : NIDHI DEOUSKAR (2017), INFLUENCE OF SELF AWARENESS ON SOCIAL SKILLS-AS A PART OF EMOTIONAL QUOTIENT, International Journal of Human Resource & Industrial Research, ISSN: 2349 –3593 (online), ISSN: 2349 –4816 (print), Vol.4,(Issue17,Jan-2017), pp 32–pp37, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.293794>

INFLUENCE OF SELF AWARENESS ON SOCIAL SKILLS-AS A PART OF EMOTIONAL QUOTIENT

Dr Nidhi Deouskar,

Associate Professor,
Oriental College of Management,
Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India

Abstract

Self awareness is the capability to understand the emotions and their realization which helps us to manage ourselves better individually as well as socially. The development of good interpersonal skills is paramount to success in our life and career. In today's well-connected world, everyone has immediate access to products developed through complex technology. Technology has also helped to strengthen social media through which these days people interact, hence social skills have become more important in today's world. In other words social skills are required to improve our interpersonal communication through verbal, non-verbal & symbolic formats. These social skills become more powerful with the proper use of emotions. This may be called as emotional intelligence and the measure of which may be called as emotional quotient. In other words this EQ may better be utilized to understand, negotiate & empathize with others. In a more responsive way one can say higher the social skills, higher is the EQ & thereby higher success in corporate & personal life. Goleman proposed that leaders scoring high in emotional intelligence are instrumental in organizational success. Thus social skills and emotional intelligence which is the capacity to be aware of, control and express one's emotions and to handle interpersonal relationships judiciously and empathetically have become all the more important.

The purpose of the study is to examine the relationship of self awareness and social skills amongst the people. Emotions play a very crucial role in our life. Emotional intelligence refers to the ability to understand and recognize emotions in ourselves and others. If the managers attain full control over their emotional status, they will be more accepted socially and would be able to generate cooperation among others. Through a Judgmental method suitable respondents were selected. A questionnaire was administered to them in order to investigate the relation between social skills & self awareness. Goleman proposed that leaders scoring high in emotional intelligence are instrumental in organizational success. Through this study it was found out that there is a strong positive correlation between self awareness & social skills which implies that self introspection is prerequisite for a successful managerial behaviour. Organizations should encourage & organize training program on social skills and self awareness & more such activities as to enhance both intra & inter people skills for self enrichment and hence organizational development.

Design / Methodology/ Approach- *The present paper is based on primary data wherein data was collected by administering questionnaire to the respondents. It is an empirical study to understand the relationship of self awareness with social skills. Pearson correlation method was employed for analysis.*

Findings :- *The analysis showed that there is a strong relationship of self awareness with social skills and hence this study may enhance the social skills of people in general and managerial skills too in particular.*

Limitations:- *The present study was conducted on a limited sample and was generalized thereafter.*

Praactical Implications :- The research may give an insight to the organizations to conduct self awareness programs for it's managers so that they may enhance their social skills.

Originality /Value:-After review of literature it was seen that lot of studies are done on emotional Intelligence as a whole but a gap was felt for individual factors defining it .So this topic was taken concentrating on two factors of EI.

Key words:-Emotional Intelligence, Emotional Quotient, Social skills,Self awareness,Self Management

Introduction:-

Emotions play a very crucial role in our life . Emotional intelligence refers to the ability to understand and recognize emotions in ourselves and others (Goleman, 1998). **Emotional Intelligence (EQ or EI)** is a term that was coined by two researchers – Peter Salavoy and John Mayer – and popularized by Dan Goleman in his 1996 book of the name “Emotional Intelligence”. One of the most applied aspect of emotional intelligence has been is that of leadership. Goleman proposed that leaders scoring high in emotional intelligence are instrumental in organizational success; leaders must have the competency to understand employees' feelings about their work environments, to give a helping hand when problems arise, to control their own emotions in order to gain the trust of the employees, and to understand the political and social dynamics within the organization. The present day corporate world is essentially a blend of technical skills with social skills in which social skills do score higher as they are instrumental in the execution of the practical knowledge. Emotional skills can be well gauged by emotional quotient which is a measure of how efficiently one can manage his emotions well according to the situation. The concept of emotional intelligence has become a key topic of behavioral research in recent years, especially in regards to how it affects today's workforce. Human Resource form an important part of any business, so anything that impacts the efficiency of people's minds also impacts the businesses they run or work for. In fact, many experts now believe that a person's emotional intelligence quotient (EQ) may be more important than their IQ and is certainly a better predictor of success, quality of relationships, and general well being. It's interesting to note that the concept of emotional intelligence has travelled from being something called “Social Intelligence” all the way back in the 1930's, to “Emotional Strength” in the mid-20th century, to its current terminology, “Emotional Intelligence.”The concept has been further analyzed & subdivided into following parts:-

1. Self Awareness:-The capability to understand an emotion as it “happens” is the key to your EQ. Developing self-awareness requires building rapport with our true feelings. Realization about our own emotions helps to manage them well. The major elements of self-awareness are:

- Emotional awareness:- Your ability to recognize your own emotions and their effects.
- Self-confidence:- Sureness about your self-worth and capabilities.

2. Self-Management:-The ability to manage, control, and adapt our emotions, mood, reactions, and responses . . We can control our emotions by using a number of techniques to alleviate negative emotions such as anger, anxiety or depression. A few of these methods include perceiving a situation in a more positive light, taking a long walk and meditation or prayer. Self-regulation involves

- Self-control:- Managing unwanted impulses.
- Trustworthiness. Maintaining standards of honesty .
- Conscientiousness. Being responsibility for your own performance.
- Adaptability. Handling change with flexibility.
- Innovation. Being adaptive to new ideas.

3. **Motivation :-Explore** our emotions to motivate ourselves to take appropriate action, commit, follow-through, and work towards the accomplishment of our goals . To motivate oneself for any achievement requires clear goals and a positive attitude. Although we may have a predisposition to either a positive or a negative attitude, you can with effort and practice learn to think more positively. If you catch negative thoughts as they occur, we can view it in more positive terms — which will help us achieve our goals. Motivation is made up of:

- Achievement zeal:- Your constant striving to improve or to meet a standard of excellence.
- Dedication:- Aligning with the goals of the group or organization.
- Initiative. Ready to act on opportunities.
- Optimistic attitude:- Pursuing goals persistently despite obstacles and setbacks.

4. **Empathy:-** The ability to feel for others, understand their emotions, and utilize that understanding to relate to others more effectively .The ability to realize how people feel is important to success in your life and career. The more skillful you are at discerning the feelings behind others ‘emotions the better you can control the signals you send them. An empathetic person excels at:

- Service orientation. Anticipating, recognizing and meeting clients’ needs.
- Developing others. Sensing what others need to progress and enhancing their abilities.
- Leveraging diversity. Cultivating opportunities through diverse people.
- Political awareness and knowhow: - Reading a group’s emotional currents and power relationships.
- Understanding others. Discerning the feelings behind the needs and wants of others.

5. **Social skills:-**Build relationships, relate to others in social situations, lead, negotiate conflict, and work as part of a team. The development of good interpersonal skills is paramount to success in your life and career. In today’s well-connected world, everyone has immediate access to technical knowledge. Thus, “people skills” are all the more important to strike a balance now because we must possess a high EQ to better understand, empathize and negotiate with others in a global economy. Among the most useful skills are:

- Influence:- Having positive impact on others.
- Communication:- Flow of clear messages.
- Leadership:- Inspiring and guiding groups and people.
- Change agent. Initiating or managing change.
- Conflict resolution & management. Understanding, negotiating and resolving disagreements.
- Building bonds. Nurturing instrumental relationships.
- Collaboration and cooperation. Interdependence on others towards shared goals.
- Team abilities. Creating group synergy in achieving collective goals.

Why is Emotional Intelligence Important?

Physical Health – The ability to take care of ourselves and especially to manage our stress, which has a huge impact on our overall wellness, is heavily dependent on our emotional intelligence. Only by being aware of our emotional state and our reactions to stress in our lives can we maintain good health.

Mental Well-Being – Emotional intelligence affects our perception and outlook on life. It can also help to subside anxiety and avoid depression and mood swings.

Relationships – Understanding the needs, feelings, and responses of those we care about leads to stronger and more fulfilling relationships.

Conflict Resolution – When we can value people’s emotions and empathize with their mental makeup, it’s much easier to resolve conflicts or possibly avoid them before they start. We are also better at negotiation . It’s easier to give people what they want if we can perceive what it is.

Success – Higher emotional intelligence helps us to be stronger internal motivators, increase self-confidence, and improve our ability to achieve our goals.

Leadership – The ability to understand what motivates others, relate in a positive manner, and to build stronger bonds with others in the workplace inevitably makes those with higher emotional intelligence better leaders. An effective leader can recognize what the needs of his people are, so that those needs can be met in a way that encourages higher performance and workplace satisfaction. It was found that level of emotional intelligence had a significant relationship with transformational leadership style (Mandell & Pherwani, 2003).

Literature Review:-

The concept of EI was first proposed by Salovey and Mayer (1990, 1994, p. 773) who define it as “a form of social intelligence that involves the ability to monitor one’s own and others’ feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them, and to use this information to guide one’s thinking and action.” The ability model of EI proposed by Salovey and Mayer (1990) consisted of four dimensions: (1) the ability to perceive, appraise and express emotion; (2) the ability to generate feelings when they facilitate thought; (3) the ability to understand emotion; and (4) the ability to regulate emotion. Goleman (1995) popularized Salovey and Mayer’s model to reinforce how emotional intelligence differs from cognitive intelligence in his book *Emotional Intelligence: Why It Can Matter More Than IQ*. Goldman went on to define EI as the ability to recognize and regulate our own feelings and the feeling of others. EI was described by Bar-On (1997, p.1) as “an array of personal, emotional, and social abilities, and skills that influence and individuals’ ability to cope with effectively with his or her given environmental demand and pressures.” Although there are various definitions of EI, two distinct approaches exist in understanding the nature of EI. The ability approach mainly focuses on emotion-related cognitive ability to effectively join emotion and reasoning. The ability EI must be measured by maximum performance tests (Mayer & Salovey, 1997). On the other hand, the trait approach, proposed by Bar-On (1997), involves emotion-related behavioral dispositions and self-perceived abilities and use self-report measures. However, some researchers have doubted the validity and reliability of the EI construct. For example, EI has been criticized as an “invalid concept” (Locke, 2005). Although there are some criticisms regarding the various concepts and measurement of EI construct, there is also a growing body of literature emphasizing the importance of EI (Goleman, 1995; George, 2000; Law, Wong, & Song, 2004).

. For example, Langhorn (2004) has investigated the relationship between EI of managers and performance in the pub restaurant and Sy, Tram and O’Hara (2006) have explored the effects of EI on job satisfaction and job performance in the restaurant setting. Furthermore, previous studies on EI have mainly focused on EI of managers, whereas few empirical studies have been conducted to examine EI of employees. It is important to examine EI of employees in the hospitality industry, given their frequently direct interaction with customers. Barlow and Maul (2000) found service providers’ EI is strongly associated with customer satisfaction. Van Rooy, Alonso and Viswesvaran (2005) have made a study in which a common measure of emotional intelligence was administered to 275 participants. (216 female) to examine how different groups score on a test of EI differences were compared for age. Results indicated that emotional intelligence scores tended to increase with age. Chapman and Hayslip (2006) have made a cross sectional analysis in order to measure emotional intelligence in young and middle adulthood. And it was found mid life adults reported significantly greater use of optimism (a component of emotional intelligence) as a mood regulation strategy than was reported by young adults. Study done by Saranya and Velayudhan (2008) among 30 male and 30 female, university students regarding gender differences in emotional intelligence revealed that there exists no significant difference in self awareness, self regulation, social awareness and social skills among day scholars boys and girls. However, Gowdhaman and Murugan (2009) have been reported a significant effect of gender on emotional intelligence, in their study among 300 B.Ed teacher trainees. Jadhav and Havalappanavar (2009) investigated the level of emotional intelligence among male and female police constable trainees (N=200). Results revealed that women police constable (WPC) trainees have scored significantly high on emotional intelligence than their counterparts. Mayer and Salovey (1997) have suggested that individuals from different sub-cultures approach emotions differently. According to Sibia, Srivastava and Misra (2003) EI, differ across cultures. Kumar and Bhushan (2006) have examined the relationship among emotional intelligence and interpersonal

communication practices (IPC); among 120 male students of IIT Guwahati. Results revealed that IPC neither correlated with EI. Dimensions of interpersonal communication were found to be negatively correlated with self management and social skill dimension of emotional intelligence.

Purpose & Organisational Context

The purpose of this study is to investigate the influence of self awareness on the social skills which are a part of Emotional Intelligence as stated by Daniel Goleman. As most of the research in this field to date has focused on holistic EQ and it's impact , to address this gap in the literature this research tries to find out the influence of two of it's major constituents .

Significance of the Study:-

It is the intention of the researchers to be able to enhance the social skills of the managers and leaders in the working. If relationship is established between self awareness and social skills then the trainers will get a particular direction and tool to work in .

Research Questions

For the purpose of the study the following hypothesis was taken

H0:-There is no relationship between self awareness and social skills.

H1:-There is a positive relationship between self awareness and social skills.

Research Methodology :-

Research Methodology Due to the purpose and objective of this research, the fact that all three of the variables are quantitative variables and as the researcher has chosen to adopt an objective, positivist, deductive approach to the research, a quantitative methodology will be applied. Quantitative research is the systematic scientific investigation of properties and phenomena and their relationships with the ultimate aim being quantification of the variation between the phenomena (Kumar, 1999)

Research Sample:-

The population from which the sample was drawn consisted of working and non working population from all walks of life . The sample population range in age from 21 – 35 and have between 4 and 14 years experience within the Bank of Ireland. This is an example of both convenience and purposive sampling.

Data Collection :-

Data Collection Data was collected by means of a questionnaire. Questionnaires are commonly used in formal analytical surveys and are a widely used research tool in the current research domain of this study. This in part is due to the fact that they can be developed to explore or measure attitudes, opinions, behavior, level of knowledge, life circumstances or other issues and they can provide quantitative and/or qualitative data (Babbie, 1990)

Sample size:-In a small pilot study it was found that the variance was not very high to the type of questions designed to investigate this relationship. Hence a small sample size would not have a very significant effect on the outcome.

Correlations

		self awareness	social skills
self awareness	Pearson Correlation	1	.653**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.002
	N	20	20
social skills	Pearson Correlation	.653**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	
	N	20	20

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Conclusion & Organizational implications :-It is seen by the above analysis that there is a strong positive correlation between self awareness and social skills. The more we know about our self the more effective we will be in handling people effectively .It also suggest that one should invest some time in inward introspection so that outer management becomes easy.As we go up in the hierarchical level people skills become more important .Organizations should encourage activities that will enhance the people skills of the managers and will help them to understand the shortcomings and scope of improvement for them . .

References:-

1. Mayer, J. D., Caruso, D., & Salovey, P. (1999). Emotional intelligence meets traditional standards for intelligence. *Intelligence*, 27.
2. Mayer, J. D., Salovey, P., & Caruso, D. R. (2000). Models of emotional intelligence. In R. J. Sternberg (Ed.). *Handbook of Intelligence* (pp. 396-420). Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press.
3. Babbie, E., (1990). *Survey research methods.*, Belmont, CA: Wadsworth Publishing
4. Brewerton, P., & Millward, L. (2001). *Organisational Research Methods: A guide for students and researchers*. London: Sage
5. Grey, D. E., (2004), *Doing Research in the Real World*, London: Sage Publications
6. Kumar, R., (1999). *Research Methodology: A step by step guide for beginners*, London: Sage Publications
7. Daniel Goleman(2006)” *Emotional Intelligence: Why It Can Matter More Than IQ*” Bantam Books
8. Deepak Chawala(2011) “*Research Methodology: Concepts and Cases*”